

STRATEGIC COMMUNICATION SKILLS FOR ACHIEVING MEASURABLE OUTCOMES IN ENGLISH LEARNING

Catherine Teresa Alphonsa

Teacher, Faculty of English, St. Nicholas School, Neerodithurai, Tamil Nadu, India

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19203111>

Abstract: This thesis proposes an innovative approach to learning English effectively, particularly for engineering professionals who must meet the demands of today's challenging global environment. In the era of globalization, English has become an essential tool for communication, especially in marketing, business, technology, and the knowledge economy.

A common issue in contemporary college teaching and learning practices is the predominant emphasis on theoretical knowledge delivery through traditional teaching methods. Institutions often focus more on testing cognitive abilities rather than developing practical communication skills, innovation, and market-oriented competencies. However, in an increasingly competitive and information-driven world, English serves as a vital instrument for acquiring academic knowledge and professional expertise.

Therefore, there is a pressing need to adopt alternative and effective teaching methodologies that enhance practical communication skills and align with outcome-based education. By integrating innovative strategies and learner-centered approaches, students can be better prepared to excel professionally and meet global standards.

Keywords: Communication Skills; English Language Learning; Learning Styles; Outcome-Based Education; Engineering Professionals; Teaching Methods; Globalization.

Introduction

Nowadays many graduates did not get placements to get a good job in a corporate company. The main reason for this cause is that their inaccuracy in their communication skills. In all the colleges' proper curriculum is prepared for making the students to improve their communication skills. But the syllabus for the university did not satisfy the ultimate aim of the university. This is not a mistake in the syllabus. But it a mistake in the teaching methodology and the way of teaching the subject. Because the examination conducted by the university which allot the marks for the presentation only. So the ability of an individual

did not be correctly tested by examination. So many students are following the learning methodology by just theoretically studying the syllabus for their exams. So while they come out of the college they cannot able to tackle the situation of communicating with the co-operate heads. So we are go for different learning styles and strategies for teaching and English language to the students. The five different learning styles that I proposed is given below

1) By motivate the students and mould the students to present a topic effectively

2) Sample mock interviews can be conducted among the students to make the students to realize their professionalism

3) Group of students can be formed together to act as a human resource officer and ask them to conduct interview among the students and choose a right candidate for the right job

4) Moulding the students with more confident by making them to wear neat dress and trained them to walk smart.

5) Proper training is given for making the students to be self-confident, self-esteem and self-respect.

By following these learning styles the self-confidence of the particular individual is increased. So that he/she can communicate with more confidence with the corporate heads and it will make a way of getting a good position to reach maximum height. Also while following these methodologies, the discipline will automatically come within them. So they can get more platforms to show their individual talents and share their thoughts.

By proper motivation the mind and the whole body will get energized to do something different for the development of them and also it leads to the development of the society.

Purpose of making different Learning Styles

To introduce participants to different learning styles and how to apply them to their study Skills

- To learn about learning styles.
- To understand the differences between auditory, visual and kinesthetic learners
- To identify your own learning style

There are three basic types of learning styles. The three most common are visual, auditory, and kinesthetic. To learn, we depend on our senses to

process the information around us. Most people tend to use one of their senses more than the others. Today's lesson will help you determine which of these learning styles you rely on the most.

There is a series of 16 questions that are related to the three main learning styles. Read the question and select the answer that closest fits your answer. Don't think about the questions too much. Go with your first choice. After you answer each of these questions, just click on the submit button at the bottom of the page. If you are connected to the internet, the computer will evaluate the results and display how many of each answer you selected.

Once the computer has evaluated your answers, it will show your primary learning style. Sometimes people have two or three that all have about the same number of choices. Some people depend on two or more types of learning styles.

It is not unusual to use different learning styles for different tasks. That's why people can respond so differently to the same thing. Take the inventory and see your results. See the summary of the different learning styles.

Understanding and identifying the different styles.

1. How could knowing your learning style be of benefit to you, personally?
2. How can it be helpful in your interactions with others?
3. How do you think this could help you in your studies?
4. How do you think this could help you in lectures?
5. How do you think this could help you in note taking? Learning preferences stem from the way we

learn best. There is no right or wrong way to learn. But three basic styles of learning can be identified:

- Kinesthetic (learning by experiencing and doing)
- Auditory (learning by listening)
- Visual (learning by looking at images)

Implication of communication skills with different Ideas

The Communication Skills will develop self-confidence among the students to communicate their thoughts more effectively. The Interpersonal communication skill of an individual can be developed. Interpersonal communication is often defined by communication scholars in numerous ways, usually describing participants who are dependent upon one another. It can involve one on one conversations or individuals interacting with many people within a society. It helps us understand how and why people behave and communicate in different ways to construct and negotiate a social reality. While interpersonal communication can be defined as its own area of study, it also occurs within other contexts like groups and organizations. Interpersonal communication is the process that we use to communicate our ideas, thoughts, and feelings to another person. Our interpersonal communication skills are learned behaviors that can be improved through knowledge, practice, feedback, and reflection. Interpersonal communication includes message sending and message reception between two or more individuals. This can include all aspects of communication such as listening, persuading, asserting, nonverbal communication, and more. A primary concept of interpersonal communication looks at communicative acts when there are few

individuals involved unlike areas of communication such as group interaction, where there may be a large number of individuals involved in a communicative act.

Individuals also communicate on different interpersonal levels depending on who they are engaging in communication with. For example, if an individual is communicating with a family member, that communication will more than likely differ from the type of communication used when engaged in a communicative act with a friend or significant other. Overall, interpersonal communication can be conducted using both direct and indirect mediums of communication such as face-to-face interaction, as well as computer-mediated communication. Successful interpersonal communication assumes that both the message senders and the message receivers will interpret and understand the messages being sent on a level of understood meanings and implications. The method of implementing this concept is done by Telling, when used alone, results in 70% recall three hours later, and 10% recall three days later.

Showing, when used alone, results in 72% recall three hours later, and 20% recall three days later.

Blend of Telling and Showing results in 85% recall three hours later, and 65% recall three days later

An opportunity to develop communication skills is an important experience requirement. This applies to all areas of the work environment, including communication with supervisors, co-workers, government regulators, clients and the general public. Acceptable communication experience should give you an opportunity to participate in:

- preparing written work, including day-to-day correspondence, design briefs and major reports
- Making oral reports or presentations to co-workers, supervisors, senior management, clients and Regulatory authorities; and making presentations to the general public as such opportunities arise.

Teaching to All Types

Here are some strategies to ensure that your courses present information that appeals to a range of learning styles. These suggestions are based on the Felder-Silverman model.

I. Teach theoretical material by first presenting phenomena and problems that relate to the theory (sensing, inductive, global). For example, don't jump directly into free-body diagrams and force balances on the first day of a statics course. First describe problems associated with the design of buildings and bridges and artificial limbs, and perhaps give the students some of those problems and see how far they can go before they get all the tools for solving them.

II. Balance conceptual information (intuitive) with concrete information (sensing). Intuitors favor conceptual information--theories, mathematical models, and material that emphasizes fundamental understanding. Sensors prefer concrete information such as descriptions of physical phenomena, results from real and simulated experiments, demonstrations, and problem-solving algorithms. For example, when covering concepts of vapor-liquid equilibria, explain Raoult's and Henry's Law calculations and nonideal solution behavior, but also explain how these concepts relate to barometric pressure and the manufacture of carbonated beverages.

III. Make extensive use of sketches, plots, schematics, vector diagrams, computer graphics, and physical demonstrations (visual) in addition to oral and written explanations and derivations (verbal) in lectures and readings. For example, show flow charts of the reaction and transport processes that occur in particle accelerators, test tubes, and biological cells before presenting the relevant theories, and sketch or demonstrate the experiments used to validate the theories.

IV. To illustrate an abstract concept or problem-solving algorithm, use at least one numerical example (sensing) to supplement the usual algebraic example (intuitive). For example, when presenting Euler's method for numerical integration, instead of simply giving the formulas for successive steps, use the algorithm to integrate a simple function like $y = x^2$ and work out the first few steps on the chalkboard with a hand calculator.

V. Use physical analogies and demonstrations to illustrate the magnitudes of calculated quantities (sensing, global). For example, tell your students to think of 100 microns is about the thickness of a sheet of paper and to think of a mole as a very large dozen molecules. Have them pick up a 100 ml. bottle of water and a 100 ml. bottle of mercury before talking about density.

VI. Occasionally give some experimental observations before presenting the general principle, and have the students (preferably working in groups) see how far they can get toward inferring the latter (inductive). For example, rather than giving the students Ohm's or Kirchoff's Law up front and asking them to solve for an unknown, give them experimental voltage/current/resistance data for

several circuits and let them try to figure out the laws for themselves.

VII. Provide class time for students to think about the material being presented (reflective) and for active student participation (active). Occasionally pause during a lecture to allow time for thinking and formulating questions. Assign "one-minute papers" near the end of a lecture period, having students write on index cards the lecture's most important point and the single most pressing unanswered question. Assign brief group problem-solving exercises in class that require students to work in groups of three or four.

VIII. Encourage or mandate cooperation on homework (every style category). Hundreds of research studies show that students who participate in cooperative learning experiences tend to earn better grades, display more enthusiasm for their chosen field, and improve their chances for graduation in that field relative to their counterparts in more traditional competitive class settings.

IX. Demonstrate the logical flow of individual course topics (sequential), but also point out connections between the current material and other relevant material in the same course, in other courses in the same discipline, in other disciplines, and in everyday experience (global). For example, before

References

Anderson, L. J. (2006). Challenging accepted wisdom about the place of conceptions of teaching in university teaching improvement. *International Journal of Teaching and Learning in Higher Education*, 18(2), 112–119.

discussing cell metabolism chemistry in detail, describe energy release by glucose oxidation and relate it to energy release by nuclear fission, electron orbit decay, waterfalls, and combustion in fireplaces, power plant boilers, and automobiles. Discuss where the energy comes from and where it goes in each of these processes and how cell metabolism differs. Then consider the photosynthetic origins of the energy stored in C-H bonds and the conditions under which the earth's supply of usable energy might run out.

Conclusion

A learning style model is useful if balancing instruction on each of the model dimensions that meets the learning needs of essentially all students in a class. The five learning styles I've discussed in this paper satisfy this criterion. Which model educators choose is almost immaterial, since the instructional approaches that teach around the cycle for each of the learning styles are essentially identical. Whether educators are designing a course or curriculum, writing a textbook, developing instructional software, forming cooperative learning teams, or helping students develop interpersonal, leadership, and communication skills, they will benefit from using any of these models as the basis of their efforts.

Baker, M. T., & Coleman, S. K. (1982). *Qualitative research for education: An introduction to theory and methods*. Boston: Allyn & Bacon.

Blake, J. F. (2003). Teacher cognition in language teaching: A review of research on what language teachers think, know, believe, and do. *Language Teaching*, 36(2), 81–109.

Bryant, H. D. (2001). *Teaching by principle: An interactive approach to language pedagogy*. New York: Longman.

Carter, S. A., Morrison, D. R., Irvine, P. J., & Sinclair, J. (1995). *Beginning teacher education students' conceptions of teaching and approaches to learning*. *Australian Journal of Teacher Education*, 20(1), 19–29.

Dawson, G. R. (1990). *Foreshadowing conceptions of teaching*. *Research and Development in Higher Education*, 13, 291–297.

Ellis, P. B. (1989). *Approaches to the enhancement of tertiary teaching*. *Higher Education Research and Development*, 8, 7–26.